

Theory and practice of education

UDC 37.015.3:378(460):81'243(043.3)

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18006792>

Actualization of multilingual education in Spanish universities in the formation of a polycultural personality

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Accepted: 14.11.2025 | Published: 30.11.2025

Abstract. *The aim of the article is a comprehensive analysis of the current state of multilingual education in Spanish universities, identification of its sociolinguistic prerequisites, pedagogical features and challenges, as well as outlining the leading trends in the development of multilingual educational models in the context of globalization and preservation of regional linguistic heritage. Methods.* To achieve the set goal, a set of theoretical methods was applied: analysis of regulatory documents, comparative pedagogical analysis of regional models of multilingual education, generalization of research results and scientific publications, analysis of methodological practices of universities, as well as interpretation of pedagogical concepts, in particular CLIL and “dominant language constellations”. **Results.** The article establishes that multilingual education in Spain is the result of a long historical process of democratization and linguistic decolonization, which ensured the official status of the Catalan, Basque and Galician languages. It is proven that modern

language policy is based on the principles of inclusive multilingualism aimed at developing cognitive flexibility, intercultural competence and professional mobility of students. The role of CLIL as a universal methodological model that combines the linguistic, cognitive and cultural components of learning is analyzed. The effectiveness of interactive methods and digital technologies, in particular the method of digital storytelling, in the formation of a polycultural personality is revealed. Key problems are identified: imbalance between state, regional and foreign languages, lack of multilingual resources, the need to train teachers to work in a multilingual environment and weak representation of multilingualism in digital communication of universities.

Conclusions. *The results of the study confirm that the Spanish model of multilingual education successfully integrates regional linguistic diversity and global communicative challenges, contributing to the formation of a generation of students with a high level of tolerance, critical thinking and the ability to intercultural interaction. Despite the existing challenges, its development is determined by the gradual transition to innovative digital and pedagogically balanced educational practices.*

Keywords: *multilingual education, intercultural competence, polymulticultural personality, language policy of Spain, interactive methods, digital technologies, universities of Spain.*

Актуалізація мультилінгвального навчання в університетах Іспанії у формуванні полікультурної особистості

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Анотація. *Метою* статті є всебічний аналіз сучасного стану багатомовної освіти в університетах Іспанії, визначення її соціолінгвістичних передумов, педагогічних особливостей та викликів, а також окреслення провідних тенденцій розвитку багатомовних освітніх моделей у контексті глобалізації та збереження регіональної мовної спадщини. **Методи.** Для досягнення поставленої мети застосовано комплекс теоретичних методів: аналіз нормативно-правових документів, порівняльно-педагогічний аналіз регіональних моделей багатомовної освіти, узагальнення результатів досліджень і наукових публікацій, аналіз методичних практик університетів, а також інтерпретація педагогічних концепцій, зокрема CLIL та «домінантних мовних констеляцій». **Результати.** У статті встановлено, що багатомовна освіта Іспанії є результатом тривалого історичного процесу демократизації та лінгвістичної деколонізації, що забезпечила офіційний статус каталонської, баскської та галісійської мов. Доведено, що сучасна мовна політика базується на принципах інклюзивного мультилінгвізму, спрямованого на розвиток когнітивної гнучкості, міжкультурної компетентності та професійної мобільності студентів. Проаналізовано роль CLIL як універсальної методичної моделі, що поєднує мовну, когнітивну та культурну складові навчання. Розкрито ефективність інтерактивних методів та цифрових технологій, зокрема метод цифрових розповідей, у формуванні полікультурної особистості. Визначено ключові проблеми: дисбаланс між державною, регіональними та іноземними мовами, нестача багато мовних ресурсів, необхідність підготовки викладачів до роботи у багатомовному середовищі та слабка представленість мультилінгвізму в цифровій комунікації університетів. **Висновки.** Результати дослідження підтверджують, що іспанська модель багатомовної освіти успішно інтегрує регіональне мовне розмаїття та глобальні комунікативні виклики, сприяючи формуванню покоління студентів із високим рівнем толерантності, критичного мислення та здатності до міжкультурної взаємодії. Попри наявні труднощі, її розвиток визначається поступовим

переходом до інноваційних цифрових і педагогічно збалансованих освітніх практик.

***Ключові слова:** мультилінгвальна освіта, міжкультурна компетентність, полікультурна особистість, мовна політика Іспанії, інтерактивні методи, цифрові технології, університети Іспанії.*

Introduction. The actualization of multilingual education in Spain is due to its unique linguistic situation, because along with the state Spanish (Castilian) language, several official regional languages function in the country – Catalan, Basque and Galician. Such linguistic diversity creates specific conditions for the organization of higher education, which combines the preservation of regional languages, the development of national identity and integration into the global educational space. After the adoption of the 1978 Constitution, which provided the official status of minority languages, Spanish higher education gradually formed a model of multilingual education, focused both on supporting local linguistic traditions and on international communication. In modern conditions, the processes of globalization, the strengthening of the role of English as an international means of communication, as well as the need to train specialists capable of working in a multicultural environment, have led to the spread of three-component multilingual education models in Spanish universities: regional language – Spanish – English. These trends are accompanied by didactic innovations, in particular digital narrative practices, and the growing role of digital multilingual communication. At the same time, certain difficulties related to the balance between different languages, the provision of resources and the training of teachers persist. In this context, an analysis of multilingual education policies and practices in Spain allows us to trace how efforts to support linguistic diversity are combined with the need to respond to the challenges of a globalized world.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Modern studies of multilingual education in higher education in Spain demonstrate the growing role of multilingualism as a factor in internationalization and the formation of multicultural personality of

students. In the works of D. Lasagabaster [1; 2], multilingualism is considered as a strategic tool of universities, which at the same time reveals contradictions between institutional approaches and real practices of students. The author emphasizes that multilingualism policy can improve the quality of education, but its effectiveness depends on taking into account individual language repertoires. The methodological basis of multilingual training is the CLIL model, conceptualized by D. Coyle, P. Hood and D. Marsh [3]. Its 4Cs structure (Content, Communication, Cognition, Culture) outlines the mechanism of combining subject content, language practice and the development of intercultural competence. Earlier reviews, in particular M. Pérez Cañado [4], have shown generally positive results of CLIL, while emphasizing the need for deeper longitudinal and qualitative research on the impact of integrated learning on students' personal development.

Within the theoretical approaches, the repertoire perspective, presented by the tandems of scholars L. Aronin and E. Vetter [5], and J. Lo Bianco and L. Aronin [6], plays a significant role. Its central element is the concept of Dominant Language Constellations, which describes individual multilingual repertoires as flexible, situational combinations of language resources. This approach allows analyzing the process of forming a multicultural identity through the interaction of personal experiences, social contexts and academic practices.

D. Madrid and S. Julius [7] emphasize that the choice of English-language programs is mainly associated with the desire to increase competitiveness in the international labor market, expand academic mobility, and form a high level of global competence. The same opinion concerning the institutional dimension of multilingualism is represented by the studies of J. Cots, P. Garrett and D. Lasagabaster [8], which show how Spanish universities balance between the Anglicization of the educational environment and the support of regional languages. Their findings highlight the tension between global and local language orientations that influence students' language choices and identities. At the same time, the emphasis on macro-

level strategies means that individual educational practices require further empirical study.

A significant area of recent literature is the analysis of digital communication in universities. The study by L. Català-Oltra, R. Martínez-Gras and C. Penalva-Verdú [9] demonstrates that multilingualism in the web representations of higher education institutions does not always reflect the real language regime of the classrooms. This highlights the importance of a comprehensive approach that combines the analysis of digital resources with the study of the pedagogical technologies.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem. The current research covers three key areas: language policies, CLIL methodology, and models of individual multilingualism. They form a coherent theoretical basis for analyzing the formation of a multicultural personality, but at the same time point to gaps: a lack of longitudinal data, limited research combining macro- and micro-levels of analysis, and insufficient attention to pedagogical technologies in the real conditions of university multilingualism.

Formulation of the objectives of article (setting the task). The study aims to analyze the features of the formation and development of multilingual education in Spain, taking into account the historical context, language policy and sociocultural factors. The set goal presupposes the realization of the following objectives: 1) to identify the role of regional, state and foreign languages in preparing the modern Spanish student as a bearer of multicultural and multilingual competence; 2) to highlight effective teaching methods and technologies aimed at developing a polycultural personality, in particular interactive and research methods, as well as digital storytelling of cultural identities; 3) consider the main challenges and prospects for the development of multilingual education in Spanish universities in the context of international educational trends.

Presentation of the main research material. The actualization of multilingual education is connected with the fact that Spain is a multilingual country, where, along with the state language (Spanish – Castilian), there are official regional languages:

Catalan, Basque, Galician. Such linguistic diversity creates special conditions for multilingual education in the country's universities.

In the 20th century, the end of the Franco dictatorship (1939-1975) led to the adoption of the 1978 Constitution, which, in addition to being the basis for a return to democracy, recognized all the minority languages spoken in Spain, which traditionally did not play any role at all in many social spheres, including education. Since the main minority languages (Basque, Catalan and Galician) received the status of joint official languages with Spanish in 1978, efforts have been made to revive these languages. The common official status of minority languages has led to their use as a means of instruction in Spanish universities [2, p. 27].

In addition to minority languages, foreign languages also play a significant role in the upbringing of the multicultural personality of a Spanish student, performing cognitive, developmental and educational functions. In general, the study of foreign languages in the educational process broadens cultural horizons and contributes to the development of intercultural adaptation [4]. In particular, foreign languages ensure the development, deepening and expansion of students' cognitive cultural interests [10]. The developmental aspect includes elements related to the penetration of the culture of the countries whose languages are studied: the development of understanding of the role and place of a certain socio-cultural affiliation in the world community; the formation of the ability to navigate the value categories of the cognizable society. In the educational aspect, there is an orientation towards universal human values, the cultivation of tolerance, patriotism, self-esteem, the ability to establish and maintain interpersonal relationships in a team. Today, Spanish universities offer foreign education in English, French and German, and also support double degree programs and international internships.

It should be noted that, as a result of the rapid spread of English-language programs due to globalization processes and the importance of developing global competence in students, English-language curricula have spread in Spanish universities [7]. Therefore, Spanish higher education today is characterized by multilingual

education - based on minority languages, Spanish and English. For instance, the Autonomous University of Barcelona uses Catalan to clarify English concepts, their multilingual repertoire acts as a resource in intercultural interaction during the educational process. At the same time, bilingual regions of Spain have included other foreign languages (e.g., French and German) in their curricula to a lesser extent [11]. In this way, the process of internationalization has forced Spanish universities to find a balance between the process of preserving minority languages and the need to be part of a globalized higher education space and respond to its linguistic pressures [8; 12; 13; 14].

Thus, today, Spain's multicultural language policy contributes to the opening of new educational and research programs in universities. It should be noted that multilingualism is quite widespread in Spanish higher education, although too often it remains hidden and insufficiently studied.

A multilingual person has different languages in his or her linguistic repertoire, some of which are more active, while others are used less frequently. The term "dominant language constellation" (DLC) has been coined to refer to specific languages that are sufficient to survive in a multilingual environment for a certain period of time [5; 6]. Although the linguistic repertoire of a multilingual speaker may include skills in many different languages, DLC only covers those that are most active, which are usually "three languages that together provide the functions of human language. Often, these are the local (regional) language, the official language of the country, and the international language" [15]. Thus, the concept of DLC fits perfectly into contexts such as Spain in general and its autonomous regions, including: the Basque Country (Euskadi), Galicia, Catalonia, the Valencian Community, etc.

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) is a common approach in all Spanish universities, despite the different educational configurations and bilingual programs in the different regions of the country, including: Andalusia, Aragon, Asturias, the Balearic Islands, the Basque Country, the Canary Islands, Cantabria, Castile-La Mancha, Castile and León, Catalonia, Extremadura, Galicia, La Rioja,

Madrid, Murcia, Navarra and the Valencian Community [16, p. 141]. This systematic approach involves the combination of teaching of professional disciplines and a foreign language (mainly English), preparing students for the globalized labor market and contributing to the internationalization of higher education.

Subject-language integrated learning is based on the 4Cs concept, where 4Cs stands for “content”, “communication”, “cognition”, and “culture”. This concept, in turn, is based on the idea that the educational process should provide not only the acquisition of subject knowledge, but also the development of linguistic, cognitive, and intercultural skills [3]. The first component of this concept is content, which involves mastering the content of a specific academic discipline. In subject-language integrated learning, students learn the subject through a foreign language, so it is important that the educational material is methodically adapted and accessible for understanding by a foreign-speaking audience. The second component, communication, emphasizes the role of language as a means of learning and interaction. Students do not just passively receive information, but actively use a foreign language to discuss, analyze and complete tasks, developing academic and professional communication.

The third component – cognition – concerns the development of thinking. Subject-language integrated learning is focused on the formation of various cognitive skills: from understanding basic facts to analysis, synthesis and critical thinking. Tasks are structured so that language is not an obstacle, but a means of processing information and constructing complex mental operations. Finally, the “culture” component involves the formation of intercultural competence [17]. Since learning takes place in a foreign language, students naturally encounter other cultural contexts, ways of thinking and professional norms. This contributes to the development of tolerance, awareness of cultural diversity and the ability to work in an international environment.

Therefore, the 4Cs concept characterizes subject-language integrated learning as a multidimensional pedagogical approach where content learning, language skill development, cognitive activity, and intercultural understanding interact and reinforce each other, creating a holistic and effective educational process.

As for teaching methods, active methods are effective in terms of educating a multicultural personality, including interactive (for example, the peer learning method, during which students who speak different languages teach each other; the “flipped classroom” method with an emphasis on group interaction; the role-playing method) and research teaching methods (the project method, which involves students of different specialties and cultures to work on a common task). Interactive methods allow students to interact in the form of dialogue of different functional types: one-way dialogue-question, two-way dialogue with a variation of communicative roles, conversation support, request for additional information, exchange of opinions. Where collective intelligence, mutual assistance and creativity are needed, it is advisable to organize group work in the form of polylogue (discussion, debate, round table, etc.). In turn, research teaching methods contribute to in-depth study of the material, the development of critical and creative thinking, which contributes to the manifestation of critical thinking of the individual in any other area (e.g., social, professional, etc.). For teachers, this means the need to master methods of facilitation, group management and assessment in conditions of diversity.

Interesting, in our opinion, is the interactive method of digital storytelling about cultural identities, which combines the story of personal or collective cultural experience with digital technologies. The latter are used to create multimedia content. Note that digital storytelling can be used in both educational and research contexts. From an educational perspective, digital storytelling allows students to develop intercultural competence, become aware of their own and others’ cultural identities, increase critical thinking about stereotypes and social prejudices, and develop narrative and communication skills through the use of digital media. In addition, creating multimedia stories stimulates the exchange of knowledge and cultural practices, develops the ability to work in a team and adapt to different cultural contexts. In turn, in socio-cultural research, digital storytelling is used to document cultural heritage, oral histories and traditions, making them accessible to a wide audience.

The narrative component of this method may include personal stories, family narratives, stories about regional cultural practices or traditions that form individual or collective cultural identity. Multimedia tools can be audio, video, photos, animation and interactive presentations that allow you to bring the story to life and make it more visual and attractive to the audience. Accordingly, various technological tools are used to implement digital storytelling: video editors and animation programs, podcast platforms, web platforms for interactive stories, as well as social networks and blogs for sharing and discussing stories/narratives. An important feature is interactivity: students from different cultures can comment, exchange experiences and create common narratives, which contributes to effective dialogue between cultures. Digital storytelling of cultural identities combines technologies and narrative practices, allowing to realize and respect cultural diversity, develop a creative approach to learning and researching culture, form intercultural competence and digital literacy through practical experience, which in general ensures the formation of students' multimodal literacy as a component in the upbringing of a multicultural personality.

Along with the above, it should be emphasized that the possibilities of a foreign language in the upbringing of a multicultural personality are limitless, but the number of teaching hours is limited. Analysis of methodological literature and our work experience shows that the process of forming a multicultural personality depends on the organization of the educational process, its didactic, thematic and qualitative content, relevance and timeliness.

Thus, language policy is mainly focused on ideologies that are assimilationist, pluralistic or inclined to internationalism. The first two ideologies study the relationship between languages or language variations that coexist in a country in order to decide how many languages or language variations should be officially recognized. The latter defines the area from which the standard to be chosen and codified will be taken. This can be either a local language (or a language variation) or a universal language (or another variant used in society as a standard elsewhere). On the other hand, inclusive multilingualism reflects the educational development of awareness of

the importance of multilingual competences for participation in democratic and other social processes in EU countries. By implementing an inclusive multilingual policy, Spanish educators are obliged to teach communicative tools from which speakers can make and agree on linguistic decisions, and the teaching of Global English can even facilitate the entry of others into the European discourse. H. Janssen [18] argues in favor of English, stating that the competent use of English ensures the dominance of the speaker in any type of communication between speakers from European countries. In this regard, mastery of English is an integral goal of Spanish university studies. Thus, if the study of global English in a multilingual environment is limited, as some authors suggest, the expected result will be the strengthening of linguistic discrimination. Neglecting these guidelines can provoke serious linguistic conflicts and the formation of new, more negative attitudes towards English and/or the introduction of English from outside or from above, which, in turn, can only be perceived as a kind of linguistic imperialism.

The conclusion that follows from the above is that active inclusive multilingual education in Spain is preparing a new generation of cognitively more flexible young people who successfully integrate a mixed cultural environment into their own identity and their own cognition. Multilingual education in Spanish universities not only develops students' language skills, but also intercultural competence, generally ensuring the upbringing of a multicultural personality of each student. This is critically important in a globalized world, where specialists must be able to work in an international and multilingual context. Thanks to multilingual programs in higher education in Spain, its students become more tolerant and culturally sensitive, that is, able to understand and respect cultural differences, values, norms of behavior and worldviews of other people. At the same time, attention should also be paid to the challenges that exist today in the multilingual educational environment of higher education in Spain. In particular, there is a problem of balance between the state (Spanish), regional and foreign languages (mostly English) in Spanish universities. In addition, multilingual universities, such as the Polytechnic University of Valencia and

the University of the Basque Country, face coordination problems between content specialists and teachers of English for specific purposes. In addition, some universities have difficulties in defining the role of English in relation to regional languages. There is also an urgent need for adequate educational resources in several languages and for teachers to be trained in multilingual teaching [1; 2]. Spanish educators [9] argue that communication in different languages in digital channels is quite low: studies show that Spanish universities pay attention to multilingualism on university websites, but much less on social networks.

Therefore, we conclude that, despite the challenges, the Spanish multilingual language policy contributes to the formation of a generation of cognitively flexible, culturally sensitive and open to global interaction students, for whom multilingualism becomes a tool for professional growth, intercultural understanding and personal development.

Conclusions. The study shows that multilingual education in Spain is the result of a long socio-historical process aimed at combining the preservation of regional languages with the requirements of a globalized world. Modern Spanish language policy, based on the principles of inclusive multilingualism, contributes to the formation of students with a high level of cognitive flexibility, critical thinking, tolerance and the ability to intercultural interaction. It is important that multilingualism is considered not only as a means of linguistic development, but also as a key component of personal and professional development.

Spanish universities are actively implementing CLIL programs, integrating English as a global language of academic and professional communication, while maintaining the significant role of regional languages. The effective use of interactive and research methods, as well as digital technologies, such as digital storytelling, contributes to the development of intercultural competence and increasing students' motivation to learn languages.

However, multilingual Spanish education faces a number of challenges: the need to balance the use of different languages in teaching, the lack of educational resources

in several languages, the need for qualified teachers capable of working in multilingual classrooms, and the insufficient representation of multilingualism in university digital communication. Despite this, the general trend indicates significant progress in the direction of building a multilingual, culturally sensitive and innovative educational environment.

Thus, the Spanish model of multilingual education demonstrates that the combination of regional linguistic heritage and global communicative needs contributes to the education of a new generation of students capable of effective interaction in an international, multicultural and multilingual space, which makes multilingualism a significant factor in personal, academic and professional development.

Further research could focus on identifying typical DLCs for different groups of students and how multilingual environments influence the formation of language repertoires and cognitive flexibility.

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